

8. Supplementary Material

This paper is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews the related literature and theoretical background, placing our work in the context of previous studies on relational reasoning and transfer learning. Section 3 provides a detailed description of the methods and experimental design, including the specifics of the TI, SI, and downstream RNN sorting tasks, as well as the analytical techniques employed to evaluate the latent representations. Section 4 presents our experimental results, and Section 5 offers an in-depth discussion of the implications of our findings. Section 6 (now Section 8.1) outlines directions for future work, and Section 7 presents our conclusions. Section 8 contains Supplementary Material, where we describe specifics of our model architecture, training, task design, and stimuli, as well as additional work.

8.0 Limitations

We did not observe the same results each time, with the pretrained encoder underperforming on some runs. Our hypothesis was that the latent space did not always contain the same quality of rank order. After limited testing, this hypothesis was supported — we will, however, do more systematic testing of this in the future.

8.1 Future Work

Building on the encouraging results presented in this study, several promising directions for future research are evident. First, we plan to conduct a more granular analysis of the temporal dynamics of latent representation formation. By applying influence functions and mutual information measures at multiple stages during training, we aim to determine the precise point at

which the abstract rank order stabilizes and how this stabilization impacts downstream task performance.

For the ordinal tasks in sequences of integers, an interesting avenue for further investigation is the study of the influence different learning rate combinations have on training results in the fine tuning setups. In addition, fine tuning only the first layer in the trained network could help mitigate catastrophic forgetting and shed light on the utility of hidden representations across tasks.

8.2 Model Architecture

(The neural networks for TI task and RNN task will be referred to as *Binary Operator* and *RNN Model* respectively in the rest of the sections)

The *Binary Operator* consists of two encoders that share the same weights and a linear output layer. Each encoder is of two linear layers with LeakyReLU activations, whilst the *RNN Model* is an encoder followed by a standard RNN layer and an output linear layer (Fig 1-F).

The models trained on integer sequences in the single task setups were fully connected feedforward neural networks with the following architecture:

- Input layer: the size follows the input size in each task.
- Hidden layers: Three fully connected layers, the first and last having the same number of units and the middle layer half of this number. They were each followed by a ReLU activation.
- Output layer: A single fully connected layer with 2 output units, followed by a softmax activation for classification.

In the multitask and fine-tuning setups the networks had different input layer sizes depending on the task type. The rest of the layers were the same as those of the single task models.

8.3 Task Design

In the TI task, given a predefined order of n items, the training set consists of adjacent item pairs, while the testing set comprises non-adjacent pairs. Each pair is represented as a concatenated vector. The corresponding RNN Sorting task follows the same predefined order, requiring the model to process one pair at a time and incrementally construct an ordered sequence of all previously encountered items. Sequence length (the number of pairs) is preliminarily chosen as 6 for all experiments.

The TI task uses a feedforward network with two shared-weight MLP encoders for input pairs, one or two hidden layers for latent representation, and an output layer predicting the binary outcome (e.g., "first item $>$ second"). See the Supplement for details.

8.4 Stimuli

In the Transitive Inference (TI) and the RNN Sorting Task, random orthonormal vectors of length n are used as n items' encodings. More specifically, each of a vector's entry is sampled from $\mathcal{N}(0, 1)$; then Gram-Schmidt orthogonalization and normalization are applied to all n vectors to yield n random orthonormal vectors. All experiments were performed with $n = 8$.

8.5 Training Procedures

8.5.1 Training Binary Operator on TI

Training is conducted using a binary cross-entropy loss function and optimized with weighted Adaptive Momentum (AdamW). Key hyperparameters, including learning rate $1e-2$, batch size 4, and network width 8, were selected based on preliminary experiments.

In the TI task, the total number of items in the preset orders is chosen as 8. Since the train data are all adjacent pairs while the test data are all non-adjacent pairs, the training-set size and the testing-set size are 14 and 42 respectively.

8.5.2 Training RNN Model on RNN Sorting Task

Training is conducted using a customized cross-entropy loss function and optimized with AdamW. Hidden dimension of the RNN layer is chosen as 16. The RNN model is trained with a learning rate of 0.01 for 100 epochs.

8.5.3 Additional Plots of Latent Space

S1.

S2.

S3.

S1. Model 2: Rank order in latent representations (lower quality)

S2. Model 3: Randomness in latent representations

S3. Models 4 & 5: Trained on Sorting

8.6 Additional Work

8.6.1 Families

Following TI and other simple tasks, we attempted to tackle a more challenging setting involving two relations rather than one. In TI and similar tasks, it was possible to keep the relation “implicit”: i.e. we could show a network two items and ask for an output without specifying the relation type. We introduced a Families Task, in which the network had to learn relationships from an underlying graph structure containing PARENT_OF and SIBLING_OF edges. In this setting, it became necessary to feed the relation type to the model as a context variable. This problem proved challenging, and while models memorize training data successfully, work is ongoing to find a model that is able to generalize to a test set. We tried to recode the task as a sequential prediction task to see if this would improve generalization (see Section 8.7.2).

8.6.2 Families with Sequence

We also experimented with casting the family relation task into a sequential one with an RNN. Arbitrary ASCII characters of length 2 encode each family member in the dataset and two special characters are used to denote a sibling or parent relation between two members. A single delimiter character is used to separate relations in the sequence. Each sequence has 16 within-family relations in total (10 negative, 6 positive). At each step, the RNN takes as input the current character and the previous timestep's true label, thus training via "teacher forcing". The RNN outputs a 0/1 at each timestep and we mask RNN outputs at the delimiter positions as the training signal. Thus the RNN labels the relation it immediately saw indicating whether the relation IS_PARENT or IS_SIBLING based on the relation's symbol. For each sequence

instance, we ignore the first relation's contribution to the loss computation as the network should not have enough information to correctly answer the task.

8.6.3 Detailed Results for Ordinal Tasks

The pair of tasks involving a notion of order in sequences of integers yielded the following detailed results:

- Evaluation of single and multi task models:
 - single-task model on task one accuracy: 99.61%
 - single-task model on task two accuracy: 84.28%
 - multitask model accuracy for task one: 74.02%
 - multitask model accuracy for task two: 82.52%.

Ordinal tasks: the single and multitask model losses for 100 epochs

- RSA on single and multi task models:
 - task one vs task two: -0.0019
 - task one vs multitask: 0.8633
 - task two vs multitask: 0.4083

The representations from task one seemed to dominate in the multitask setup with higher RSA values between task one and multitask networks compared to task two and multitask networks.

Ordinal tasks: RDM of single task models

- Evaluation of fine-tuned networks:
 - task one before fine-tuning on task two - loss: 0.0047, accuracy: 99.8047%
 - task one after fine-tuning on task two - loss: 33.8172, accuracy: 61.0352%
 - task two before fine-tuning on task one - loss: 0.5271, accuracy: 83.2031%
 - task two after fine-tuning on task one - loss: 0.5206, accuracy: 82.0312%.
 - task two after fine tuning - loss: 0.5077, accuracy: 75.8789%
 - task one after fine tuning - loss: 0.2524, accuracy: 84.5703%
- RSA on the normally trained models and the fine-tuned models:

- task one vs trained on task two and fine-tuned on task one): 0.73241
- task one vs trained on task one and fine-tuned on task two): 0.0122
- task two vs trained on task one and fine-tuned on task two: 0.5550
- task two vs trained on task two and fine-tuned on task one: 0.0219
- trained on task two and fine-tuned on task one vs trained on task one and fine-tuned on task two: 0.0473
- trained on task one and fine-tuned on task two vs multi task: 0.2823
- trained on task two and fine-tuned on task one vs multi task: 0.6109.

8.6.4 Additional Tasks Not Covered in Main Text

Early in the work, we considered other tasks with the idea of exploring representation properties of tasks that share structural commonalities. The Subset Inclusion task is conceptually similar to the TI task but uses binary vector representations to encode items. In this paradigm, each item is represented as a binary vector, and the relation of interest is one of inclusion: an item X is considered a subset of item Y if every position where X has a value of 1 is also 1 in Y. Training is performed using pairs of items that are adjacent in an imposed ordering, ensuring that the network learns to generalize the inclusion relationship to non-adjacent pairs during testing. We found that SI and TI served as effective pretraining for one another, with either speeding up learning of the other. This suggests that the structural similarity the tasks share may contribute to improved co-performance.